

Statistical Analysis of Jump in Solar Wind Plasma Parameter and Coronal Mass Ejections with Shock Related Geomagnetic Storms

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Abstract

Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) are the drastic solar events in which huge amount of solar plasma materials are ejected into the heliosphere from the sun and are mainly responsible to generate large disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters and geomagnetic storms in the geomagnetic field. We have studied geomagnetic storms, ($Dst \leq -90nT$) observed during the period of 1997-2012 with Coronal Mass Ejections and disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters (velocity). We have inferred that most of the geomagnetic storms are associated with halo and partial-halo Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs). The association rate of halo and partial halo coronal mass ejections are found 75 % and 25 % respectively. Further, we have concluded that geomagnetic storms are closely associated with the disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters. We have determined a positive correlation between the magnitudes of geomagnetic storms and speed of CMEs with correlation coefficient 0.26. Further Positive co-relation has been found between the speed of CMEs and peak velocity of jump in solar wind plasma velocity. Statistically calculated co-relation coefficient is 0.31 between these two events. Again there is a Positive co-relation has been found between the speed of CMEs and magnitude of jump in solar wind plasma velocity with correlation coefficient 0.20. Furthermore, we observe the positive correlation between the magnitude of geomagnetic storms and the peak value of JSWV events and statistically calculated co-relation co-efficient is 0.42 between these two events. We have concluded that geomagnetic storms are mainly caused by Coronal Mass Ejections and disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters that they generate.

Introduction

Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs) are the drastic solar events in which huge amount of solar plasma materials are ejected into the heliosphere from the sun and are mainly responsible to generate large disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters and geomagnetic storms in the geomagnetic field. CMEs from the Sun drive solar wind (SW) disturbances in terms of the magnetic field, speed, and density, which in turn cause a geomagnetic disturbance in Earth [1]. Several investigators have studied geomagnetic storms with various solar features, solar wind parameters and inferred that CMEs which are the energetic solar features and associated with active regions are responsible for the most geoeffective solar wind disturbances and, therefore, the largest storms and are well associated with geomagnetic storms [2,3,4,5]. McAllister and Crooker [6] have studied the effects of solar and heliospheric phenomena on the geomagnetic field. Gopalswamy [7] has studied the role of halo and partial halo CMEs in producing geomagnetic storms.

Experimental Data

In this investigation, hourly Dst indices of geomagnetic field have been used over the period 1997 through 2012 to determine onset time, maximum depression time, the magnitude of geomagnetic storms. This data has been taken from the NSSDC Omni web data system which has been created in late 1994 for enhanced access to the near earth solar wind, magnetic field and plasma data of omni data set, which consists of one hour resolution near earth, solar wind magnetic field and plasma data, energetic proton fluxes and geomagnetic and solar activity indices. The data of coronal mass ejections (CMEs) have been taken from SOHO – large angle spectrometric, coronagraph (SOHO / LASCO) and extreme ultraviolet imaging telescope (SOHO/EIT) data. To determine disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters, hourly data of solar wind plasma velocity has been used and these data have also been taken from Omni web data also.

Data Analysis and Results

The association between geomagnetic storms of magnitude $< -90nT$ and coronal mass ejections (CMEs), and disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters for the period 1997 to 2012 are given in Table No.1. We have 54 geomagnetic storms in our list in which we have no data of CMEs for the association. From the data analysis, it is observed that 48 out of 54 (88.88%) geomagnetic storms $< -90nT$ are found to be associated

with coronal mass ejections. We have 54 geomagnetic storms in our list in which the CME data for the association is available for 48 geomagnetic storms. We have further observed that the majority of related CMEs are halo CMEs. We have 48 geomagnetic storms, which are associated with coronal mass ejections out of which 36 geomagnetic storms (75.00%) are related to the halo coronal mass ejections. Only 12 out of 48 (25.00%) geomagnetic storms are found to be associated with partial halo coronal mass ejections.

From the study of geomagnetic storms with disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters i.e. jump in solar wind plasma velocity, it is inferred that geomagnetic storms of higher magnitudes are found to be associated with such JSWV events, which have relatively higher jump magnitude of velocity. We have determined positive co-relation between magnitudes of geomagnetic storms and the peak value of jump in solar wind plasma velocity with correlation coefficient 0.42 (Figure-2).

To know the statistical behavior of shock related geomagnetic storms and CMEs we have plotted a scatter plot between the magnitude of geomagnetic storms and speed of CMEs and the resulting plot is shown in fig-3. We have observed the positive correlation between the magnitude of geomagnetic storms and the speed of associated CMEs with co-relation 0.26.

To see how the peak value of JSWV events is correlated with coronal mass ejections. We have plotted a scatter diagram between the speed of CMEs and peak value of associated JSWV events fig-4. From the trend line of the scatter plot between these two parameters, it may be concluded that there is a positive correlation between the peak value of JSWV events and speed of associated CMEs. Positive co-relation has been found between the speed of CMEs and peak velocity of jump in solar wind plasma velocity with co-relation coefficient 0.31.

To see how the magnitudes of JSWV events are correlated with speed of CMEs we have plotted a scatter diagram between the magnitude of jump in solar wind plasma velocity (JSWV) events and speed of associated CMES in fig-5. From the trend line of the scatter plot between these two parameters, it may be concluded that there is a positive correlation between magnitudes of JSWV events and speed of associated CMEs. Positive co-relation has been found between the speed of CMEs and magnitude of JSWV events with co-relation coefficient 0.20.

We have concluded that geomagnetic storms are mainly caused by Coronal Mass Ejections and disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters that they generate.

Table No.-1: Geomagnetic storms, CMEs, and Solar wind velocity.

S. No.	Geomagnetic Storms $Dst \leq -90nT$					Coronal Mass Ejections				Solar wind velocity			
	DATE	Year	Day	Hour	Magni-tude	Date	Time	Type	SPEED	Day	Hour	Maximum velocity	Magn itude of jump
1	10.01.1997	1997	10	2	-101	06.01.1997	15:10:42	Halo	136	9	14	468	101
2	10.04.1997	1997	100	19	-102	07.04.1997	14:27:44	Halo	878	99	19	473	196
3	15.05.1997	1997	135	5	-115	12.05.1997	5:30:05	Halo	464	134	9	521	250
4	03.09.1997	1997	246	15	-108	30.08.1997	1:30:35	Halo	371	245	21	560	252
5	30.12.1997	1997	364	2	-95	26.12.1997	2:31:54	Partia l	197	363	4	394	112
6	17.02.1998	1998	48	11	-114	na	na	na	NA	48	4	416	48
7	02.05.1998	1998	122	9	-203	29.04.1998	16:58:54	Halo	1374	121	10	651	255
8	07.11.1998	1998	311	11	-139	04.11.1998	7:54:06	Halo	523	310	21	639	256
9	28.02.1999	1999	59	17	-94	na	na	na	na	59	4	412	76
10	16.04.1999	1999	106	15	-156	na	na	na	na	105	15	462	89
11	12.09.1999	1999	255	7	-103	10.09.1999	7:54:05	Partia l	1467	255	2	615	204

12	22.09.1999	1999	265	19	-191	20.09.1999	6:06:05	Halo	604	265	2	602	250
13	21.10.1999	1999	294	23	-257	19.10.1999	5:50:05	Partia l	753	293	23	678	342
14	22.01.2000	2000	22	14	-98	18.01.2000	17:54:05	Halo	739	21	22	403	72
15	15.07.2000	2000	197	15	-308	14.07.2000	10:54:07	Halo	1674	197	13	1107	497
16	15.09.2000	2000	259	19	-221	12.09.2000	17:30:05	Halo	1053	259	1	401	78
17	13.10.2000	2000	287	14	-100	11.10.2000	6:50:05	Partia l	799	286	16	469	155
18	28.10.2000	2000	302	20	-142	25.10.2000	8:26:05	Halo	770	302	5	415	104
19	04.11.2000	2000	309	3	-194	01.11.2000	16:26:08	Halo	801	308	17	559	231
20	10.11.2000	2000	315	7	-102	08.11.2000	4:50:23	Halo	474	314	10	925	512
21	27.03.2001	2001	86	19	-123	25.03.2001	17:06:05	Halo	677	85	19	644	325
22	31.03.2001	2001	90	3	-413	29.03.2001	10:26:05	Halo	942	89	19	771	370
23	18.04.2001	2001	108	1	-106	15.04.2001	14:06:31	Partia l	1199	107	23	518	162
24	17.08.2001	2001	229	12	-149	15.08.2001	23:54:05	Halo	1575	229	9	599	264
25	25.10.2001	2001	298	10	-162	22.10.2001	15:06:05	Halo	1336	298	7	449	95
26	05.11.2001	2001	309	18	-314	04.11.2001	16:35:06	Halo	1810	308	18	426	114
27	24.11.2001	2001	328	6	-223	22.11.2001	23:30:05	Halo	1437	327	12	1040	612
28	29.12.2001	2001	363	22	-91	28.12.2001	20:30:05	Halo	2216	362	23	570	213
29	23.03.2002	2002	82	14	-107	22.03.2002	11:06:05	Halo	1750	82	5	504	114
30	17.04.2002	2002	107	11	-149	15.04.2002	3:50:05	Halo	720	107	6	611	286
31	11.05.2002	2002	131	13	-103	08.05.2002	13:50:05	Halo	614	131	8	522	181
32	23.05.2002	2002	143	11	-172	21.05.2002	21:50:05	Partia l	853	142	12	871	473
33	8/1/2002	2002	213	10	-98	7/29/2002	23:30:05	Partia l	360	213	0	524	157
34	30.09.2002	2002	273	1	-179	26.09.2002	1:31:44	Partia l	178	273	0	370	80
35	17.08.2003	2003	229	14	-175	14.08.2003	20:06:05	Halo	378	229	13	530	105
36	20.11.2003	2003	324	2	-417	18.11.2003	8:50:05	Halo	1660	324	2	703	262
37	03.04.2004	2004	94	14	-113	na	na	na	na	93	17	515	143
38	22.07.2004	2004	204	18	-115	20.07.2004	13:31:52	Halo	710	204	9	672	312
39	30.08.2004	2004	243	5	-116	na	na	na	na	243	17	435	63
40	07.11.2004	2004	312	19	-415	04.11.2004	9:54:05	Halo	653	312	2	730	418
41	28.05.2005	2005	148	11	-155	26.05.2005	15:06:05	Halo	586	148	1	464	185
42	12.06.2005	2005	163	16	-110	na	na	na	na	163	4	503	199
43	10.07.2005	2005	191	11	-100	09.07.2005	22:30:05	Halo	1540	190	19	474	148
44	24.08.2005	2005	236	6	-248	22.08.2005	17:30:05	Halo	2378	236	0	721	309
45	14.04.2006	2006	104	0	-111	10.04.2006	6:06:04	Partia l	183	103	0	546	165
46	14.12.2006	2006	348	14	-155	13.12.2006	2:54:04	Halo	1774	348	9	896	333
47	05.08.2011	2011	217	19	-142	04.08.2011	4:12:05	Halo	1315	216	20	605	255
48	09.09.2011	2011	252	13	-109	07.09.2011	18:48:05	Partia l	924	252	10	560	247
49	17.09.2011	2011	260	7	-94	15.09.2011	0:00:06	Partia l	530	260	1	549	185

50	26.09.2011	2011	269	13	-136	24.09.2011	12:48:07	Halo	1915	269	9	704	374
51	24.10.2011	2011	297	21	-157	22.10.2011	10:24:05	Halo	1005	296	21	534	223
52	07.03.2012	2012	67	0	-140	05.03.2012	4:00:05	Halo	1531	66	4	592	231
53	23.04.2012	2012	114	15	-119	19.04.2012	15:12:09	Partia l	540	113	20	501	205
54	17.06.2012	2012	169	0	-151	14.06.2012	14:12:07	Halo	987	168	3	519	222

Figure-1 Distribution of shock related geomagnetic storms with coronal mass ejections.

Figure-2 shows the scatter plot between magnitudes of shock related geomagnetic storms and the peak value of associated jump in solar wind plasma velocity.

Figure-3 The figure shows a scatter plot between the speed of CMEs and magnitude of shock related geomagnetic storms.

Figure-4 The figure shows a scatter plot between the speed of CMEs and peak value of JSWV events associated with shock-related GMS.

Figure-5 The figure shows a scatter plot between magnitudes of JSWV associated with shock-related GMS and speed of CMEs.

Conclusion

From our study 48 out of 54 geomagnetic storms $< -90\text{nT}$ have been identified as being associated with coronal mass ejections (88.88%), 36 out of 48 have been identified as being associated with halo coronal mass ejections and 12 out of 48 as being associated with partial halo coronal mass ejections. The association rates for halo and partial halo CMEs are found 75.00% and 25.00% respectively. The positive correlation between the magnitude of geomagnetic storms and the peak value of jump in solar wind plasma velocity suggest that coronal mass ejections and disturbances in solar wind plasma parameters play a crucial role in producing geomagnetic storms.

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